

Teaching Legal English with Contemporary and Interactive Methods

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Abstract: Due to globalization, the expansion of Uzbekistan's economic links with other nations, and the link with the expansion of strengthening at a good level, there is a growing demand for legal English teachers among professionals who speak the language. English teachers ought to assist in the development of abilities that will make law students more marketable. The method of teaching legal English is intricate but fascinating. Remember that there are a number of contemporary and interactive approaches to teaching this sublanguage. For legal English instruction to be both effective and efficient, students must use them in the classroom. Various activities of these methods are used by teachers with the aim of teaching in deeper perspective.

Key points: legal English, interactive methods, sublanguage, learning activity, legal systems.

Training that is focused on the workplace should be integrated with general language instruction. It is more advantageous to start specialized professionally-oriented training right away in groups that have a high enough level of general language training. On the other hand, in groups where English skill is low or average, the emphasis should be first on general language instruction, followed by professionally-oriented teaching. In oral communication, grammatical issues should always be worked out and corrected. It should be mentioned that there is a significant gap in the linguistic proficiency of applicants to the law faculty. Even Nevertheless, new students are typically quite motivated to study the language since they are aware of the excellent employment opportunities that come with being fluent in English lawyers. What aspects of teaching English to legal students are there? Grammar, vocabulary study, reading, and literary translation have long been the main priorities in English instruction. But the topic of how to use a foreign language practically has come up recently. Both general language instruction and professional language training should be provided in a complicated setting when teaching English to law majors. Reading real texts and using them to teach oral speech should be a part of the training curriculum from the outset.

It is crucial that students be able to freely navigate different educational and legal systems, especially in light of the issue of students studying specialization jurisprudence.

It's also important to keep in mind foreign legal systems at all times. This is crucial since there may be major differences in their legal systems. For instance, the terms "counselor" (adviser, lawyer) only exist in the USA and Ireland, whereas "solicitor" and "barrister" are exclusive to British law. After all, socialization issues are always pertinent while acquiring a second language. Teachers of law students should keep in mind that a modern specialist must speak at a level that would enable him to interact, if needed, with specialists from other nations when teaching them a foreign language. He needs to be familiar with the fundamentals of grammar in order to accomplish this, but more than anything, they need to understand legal terminology. After all, it is impossible to feel at ease in a conversational setting with other lawyers and not get lost when discussing any professional situation if a future lawyer lacks a professional vocabulary, even if they have a grammatical minimum that covers the fundamental rules of morphology and syntax and allows you to understand a foreign language text. Thus, professional vocabulary assimilation plays a major part

in law students' foreign language instruction. Lexical unit assimilation is done in order to improve oral speech abilities. It also aims to apply communication skills and provide a suitable response in typical professional communication scenarios, both written (the ability to make a resume, any legal papers, etc.) and spoken (to convey messages about a professional topic). Legal documentation and communication have specific characteristics that should be understood. Firstly, information should be transmitted in a clear and concise manner so that the recipient can be certain that the information is understood correctly. Secondly, it is important to be able to work with basic models, understand logic, and master vocabulary that has certain features in jurisprudence. This is because well-known words in jurisprudence are often translated quite differently. Lastly, when it comes to developing oral-speech skills, those with a legal orientation should be chosen from the topics of oral speech. This means that the communicative competence of law students in English should be professionally oriented.

In particular, the teacher must carefully prepare the means for conducting game activities, which can serve as various schemes, drawings, maps, slides, technical training tools, etc. Students will be very interested in various speech games. For example, playing the role of a policeman, a victim and a suspect. This may include conducting an interrogation of a suspect, describing the appearance of a suspect, conducting a trial on a civil claim, etc. It is also possible to implement the development of grammatical material using legal vocabulary. For example, when training a modal verb, you can give out cards with legal vocabulary, such as:

- ✓ He must have been arrested, but I don't know for sure if he was arrested or not.
- ✓ He could have been searched, but not searched.
- ✓ No one is obliged to testify against himself, his close relatives, etc.

To implement the educational process in this direction, an English teacher must have competent knowledge of the future profession of law students. That is, a teacher teaching English to future lawyers should be guided by legal terminology, the legal culture of the native country and the countries of the language being studied, various legal phenomena.

In conclusion, I would like to note that the effectiveness of professionally oriented legal English language teaching depends not only on the students, but also on the work of the teacher himself, who must have competent knowledge, be able to organize the educational process in such a way that students in the classroom can easily and with interest assimilate educational material. Thus, upon graduation, students should not only understand legal texts and terms, but also freely express their thoughts, communicate and also use English in their further professional activities.

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